

WAYS TO DEVELOP MARKETING MANAGEMENT METHODS IN THE ENTERPRISE

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Abstract. *This article examines market research, digital marketing, attending industry events, creating a strong brand identity, developing special products, and using analytics to implement the suggested marketing methods.*

Keywords: *production enterprise, market, product, investor, management, environment.*

INTRODUCTION. The marketing strategy of Uzbekistan is aimed at the production of products and goods at the level of market and time demand. As we mentioned above, entrepreneurs and investors are given wide economic opportunities and tax benefits for the production of such products. In particular, enterprises operating in special industrial zones were given wide-scale tax and customs benefits and preferences for a period of 3 to 7 years, depending on the volume of investments, and their connection to infrastructure facilities and communications is guaranteed. These works, of course, were one of the important factors in increasing the speed of development of developing countries, as well as

It should also be noted that localization programs introduced by our government are implemented based on the results of marketing research, which reduces the difficulty level of occupying new markets and filling markets with new types of products. The localization program is geographically focused mainly on special economic zones. In particular, the newly established free industrial and economic zones occupy a special place in the implementation of projects aimed at modernizing the production potential, which is one of the main factors of capturing new markets of our country. It can be said that in practice it pays off.

The growing importance of internal marketing in an enterprise is reflected in its organizational structure. Marketing management consists of a set of planning, organization, coordination, control, audit and promotion functions performed to increase the demand for goods and services and increase profits. Marketing management is seen as a means and philosophy of intensifying marketing activities, the purpose of which is not to organize and promote sales, but to manage demand for the company's goods and services in a competitive market. According to F. Kotler, marketing management is the formation of demand for the company's goods at the right time and in the right amount to achieve the goal before the company. J. J. Lamben described this concept as the formation and stimulation of new customer requirements. Marketing management is an activity aimed at ensuring and forming a competitive advantage of firms in the market, and it includes the following types of analysis.

1. Analysis of the external environment.
2. Situational analysis.
3. Defining the market perspective.
4. Determination of enterprise opportunities.
5. Development of market goals and strategies.
6. Planning the marketing goals of the enterprise in a specific situation.
7. Develop a marketing mix plan.

8. Implementation, organization, management, control and evaluation of the marketing plan.

Thus, marketing management manages the functional and institutional activities of marketing at various hierarchical management levels of the socio-economic system in an integrated, i.e. closely related, manner.

In the functional sense, marketing management is understood as the process of forming a decision, planning and managing its implementation.

In the institutional sense, marketing management is interpreted as leadership, management power, effective management of the achievement of the intended goal through the correct and coordinated distribution of functional tasks among all departments of the firm based on legal and organizational powers. The key factors that shape the marketing-management environment include culture, policy, and system or structure.

Come now Let's consider the economic situation in "Daka-Tex" LLC from the point of view of marketing management:

Table 1

Analysis of income, expenses and net profit of "Daka-Tex" LLC during 2018-2021

Indicators	At the end of 2018 (million soums)	At the end of 2019 (million soums)	At the end of 2020 (million soums)	At the end of 2021 (million soums)
Net income from the sale of products (goods, work and services).	50,991.18	62,262.55	58 138.12	71 248.91
Cost of goods sold (goods, work and services).	41,963.90	59,041.81	54,648.53	63 347.52
Period expenses and taxes	3 843.72	2 063.21	2 508.81	4 202.35
Net profit (loss) for the reporting period	5 236.70 (12%)	1 626.45 (3%)	1 096.73 (2%)	3 682.63 (6%)

From the analysis of the above financial reports, it is clear that the company has recorded economic growth in recent years. However, it is clear from these tables that as the income from the sale of the product increases, the cost of the product also increases. We know from the above numbers and dynamics that this has a significant negative impact on the company's net profit. This situation confirms that it is necessary to review the methods of marketing management and to apply the methods of its development in the activity of the enterprise.

We must also add that the enterprise in its activity direct work with consumers, exchange of information is not used in place of media such as advertising. As for the assortment, the number of goods that satisfy the full demand of all genders is somewhat small. Considering the fact that the company has recently started its operations, these shortcomings are invisible and can be overcome.

Taking into account the above shortcomings, from the point of view of marketing, the enterprise will have to develop its own development strategy and, of course, marketing program, relying on the principles of marketing in relation to the B2B market and customers.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Marketing management plays an important role in the success of any enterprise and it is especially important in the textile industry. We present below some of our suggestions on various ways of developing marketing management methods at Daka-Tex LLC.

These methods include market research, digital marketing, attending industry events, building a strong brand identity, developing custom products, and using analytics. Implementation of the marketing methods that we offer will help the enterprise to differentiate itself in a highly competitive market and ultimately ensure the growth of sales and profits.

The yarn and textile industry is highly competitive, with many industry players vying for market share. "Daka-Tex" LLC should develop effective marketing management methods to stand out from competitors and attract customers. We will briefly touch on the description of each of the above methods of developing marketing management methods in this enterprise:

1. Market research. Market research is a crucial step in developing effective marketing management techniques. Businesses can collect information about customer needs, preferences and behavior to inform their marketing strategies and product development. This may include identifying specific sectors, regions, or demographics that are most likely to purchase their products.

Of course, some work has been done in this regard at "Daka-Tex" LLC. But from the analysis of the last financial results of the company, we can know that these things have stopped. It is possible to benefit from today's highly competitive processes only by constantly studying market research.

2. Digital marketing. Digital marketing is very necessary in today's digital age. Businesses can develop a strong online presence through a website, social media, and other digital channels to reach and connect with customers. This includes creating high-quality content such as tutorials, product guides and industry news that provide value to customers and position the business as a leader in the industry.

If we look at the digital marketing activities of this company, we can find only the official website <https://dakatex.uz/>. In order to achieve good results in the field of digital marketing, it is necessary to use the current popular methods. For example, social network pages such as YouTube, TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, Telegram and their advertisements should be used effectively.

3. Participation in industrial events. Attending industry events such as trade shows is an effective way to showcase products, make connections and generate leads. It can also provide valuable networking opportunities and insight into the latest trends and innovations in the market.

Our research at "Daka-Tex" LLC shows that the company mainly participates in product fairs among such industrial events. However, for the development of the enterprise, it is required

to actively participate not only in product fairs, but also in industrial production, technical and international fair events.

4. Brand identity. Developing a strong brand identity is also essential to differentiate products from competitors and resonate with target audiences. Creating a consistent and memorable brand identity can help build brand awareness and customer loyalty over time. "Daka-Tex" LLC has a well-made and modern brand. But having a brand is not enough for the development of the enterprise. The company should establish a brand policy with the help of special marketing activities, PR programs for its future plans.

Figure 1. Brand of "Daka-Tex" LLC

5. Special products. Offering specialized products and services can meet unique customer needs and build loyalty. This may involve working with customers to develop custom products that meet their specific needs and preferences.

In this direction No work has been done at "Daka-Tex" LLC. The main focus will be on the development of special knitted products for participants in the framework of various sportswear, public events and charity work, and establishing cooperation with the organizers.

6. Analysis. The use of analytics is extremely important to develop effective marketing management techniques. Businesses can track marketing performance, make data-driven decisions, and market can use data analytics to continuously improve their strategies. This includes tracking website traffic, social media engagement and other metrics to measure the effectiveness of marketing campaigns.

Developing effective marketing management techniques is critical to the success of any business and is especially important in the highly competitive yarn and textile industry. By conducting market research, digital marketing, attending industry events, building a strong brand

identity, developing custom products, and using analytics "Daka-Tex" LLC can have an advantage that distinguishes it from its competitors, expand its target audience, establish strong relationships with them, and as a result, achieve sales growth and increase revenues.

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